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INTERPRETATION OF THE QUALITY OF LIFE OF PATIENTS WITH HYPERTENSION DISEASE

Abstract.

The article analyzes the obtained indicators of the quality of life of patients with hypertension stage II and III. The author used the modernized health questionnaire-36 (MOS-36 - Short-Form Health Survey, or MOS SF-36), which was developed in the USA and consists of 8 scales and 36 questions. In the work, the emphasis was placed only on the more weighty scales and questions. As a result of the conducted research, differences in the main indicators of life of practically healthy people and patients with hypertensive disease II and III stages were shown. The following indicators of quality of life were taken into account: pain sensations, mental health, role-emotional functioning, indicators of social well-being, general health and vitality. In our work, we did not take into account patients with the I stage of hypertensive disease in order to show more significant changes during the course of hypertensive disease. The article proves the decrease in quality of life assessment parameters in the main and control groups in men and women with stage III of hypertension compared to stage II. The author found a gender difference in indicators of the quality of life of men and women. In women, indicators of social well-being, general health and vital activity decreased significantly more, especially in cases with stage III hypertension (by 24.5%, 22% and 18%, respectively, $p < 0.05$). The conducted study made it possible to carefully study the respondents' answers to a list of questions that had a significant impact on the course of hypertension and the assessment of patients' quality of life.

Keywords: *quality of life, hypertension, assessment of quality of life, the survey scale, health questionnaire, the indicators of quality of life, the adapted questionnaire.*

Introduction. In the modern medical space, indicators of the effectiveness of medical measures and indicators of the patient's general condition are used to assess the quality of life (QoL). The quality of life gives a subjective assessment of the patient's feelings and depends on the completeness of his awareness. Traditionally, two conceptual approaches to assessing the quality of life are distinguished: objective and subjective [3].

According to the definition of the World Health Organization (WHO), quality of life is the perception by individuals of their position in life in the context of culture and value system and in relation to their goals, expectations, standards and problems [6].

One of the key tasks of health care is a comprehensive study of the quality of life both at the individual level (the life of an individual) and at the population level (the health of a group of people).

Arterial hypertension (AH) ranks first in prevalence among chronic non-infectious diseases in most countries of the world. About 90% of arterial hypertension is hypertension, which is diagnosed in Ukraine in 40% of women and 39% of men [4]. Undoubtedly, hypertension reduces the quality of life and leads to disability and premature death. Therefore, it is extremely important to determine which indicators need correction to improve the quality of life of hypertensive patients.

Presenting main material.

Quality of life (QoL) reflects the patient's stable feelings, which are largely subjective, as they depend on his awareness.

The purpose of the article: to evaluate and analyze the quality of life of patients with hypertension II

and III stage based on the modernized health questionnaire-36 using modified special scales and questionnaires.

Materials and methods:

To assess the quality of life of hypertensive patients, we conducted a study that included 98 patients (50 men and 48 women) who were treated at the Chernivtsi Regional Cardiology Dispensary during 2021-2023 and had a history of stage II and III hypertension. All patients were divided into 2 groups depending on the stage of hypertension. The first group included patients with II stage hypertension (28 men and 22 women); 2 – with stage III (22 men and 26 women). The average age of the examined patients was 54.5 years. In addition, the study was used modernized health questionnaire-36 (MOS-36 - Short-Form Health Survey, or MOS SF-36), which was developed in the USA and consists of 8 scales and 36 questions.

The Medical Outcomes Study Short Form 36 (MOS SF-36) questionnaire is one of the most suitable tools for assessing the quality of life of patients with hypertension. The questionnaire was developed at the Center for the Study of Medical Outcomes (USA) in 1992 by John E. Weir and Cathy Donald Sherburne. intended to assess the general health of the population in clinical practice and scientific research among patients aged 14 years and older [2].

In our work, we used a modernized and shortened version of the questionnaire, which consists of 24 items and 8 scales:

- physical functioning (FF): walking, self-care ability, physical exertion;
- role functioning (RF): ability to perform everyday work;

- pain intensity (PI): assessment of the impact of pain on the performance of daily tasks;
- general state of health (GH): the patient's subjective assessment of his state of health;
- vital activity (VA): shows the presence or absence of vital energy and lust for life;
- social functioning (SF): shows limitations of social activity depending on physical condition;

- emotional state and mental health (EM): the influence of psycho-emotional factors on the course of hypertension.

Each answer chosen by the respondent was evaluated in points. Later, the points were added up and subjected to mathematical processing. The evaluation of the measurement of indicators had a range of fluctuation from 0 to 100, where 100 is full health.

Table No. 1.

Comparative characteristics of the quality of life of practically healthy people and patients with hypertensive disease II and III stages

No	Scale normative indicators of quality of life	Practically healthy (regulations)		II stage hypertensive diseases (moderate form)		III stage hypertensive diseases (severe form)	
		males	females	males	females	h males	females
1	Physical functioning	90.5±1.4	90.5±1.2	70.2±3.1 p<0.05	72.2±3.4 p<0.05	56.2±3.3 p<0.05	58.2±3.4 p<0.05
2	Role playing physical functioning	75.7±2.4	75.7±1.3	64.1±2.5 p<0.05	64.8±2.6 p<0.05	48.1±2.5 p<0.05	52.1±2.7 p<0.05
3	Pain scale	80.1±0.6	80.2±2.5	68.4±2.6 p<0.05	68.9±2.8 p<0.05	44.6±2.6 p<0.05	48.8±2.9 p<0.05
4	General health	70.1 ± 3.5	70.1 ± 3.8	59±3.0 p<0.05	60±3.0 p<0.05	41.2±3.5 p<0.05	48.2±3.8 p<0.05
5	Viability	73.6±3.5	73.6±3.7	64.2±2.0 p<0.05	66.2±2.05 p<0.05	51.2±2.0 p<0.05	56.2±2.8 p<0.05
6	Social functioning	80.3±2.8	80.3±2.5	70.2±1.6 p<0.05	72.2±1.7 p<0.05	50.2±2.6 p<0.05	52.2±2.7 p<0.05
7	Role playing Emotional functioning	78.7±1.2	78.7±1.6	68.8±1.5 p<0.05	72.2±1.6 p<0.05	38.8±1.8 p<0.05	39.8±2.5 p<0.05
8	Mental health	68.5±1.5	68.5±1.3	58.9±2.0 p<0.05	59.4±2.5 p<0.05	44.1±2.0 p<0.05	49.2±2.5 p<0.05

As a result of the conducted research, a comparative assessment of the quality of life of men and women who did not suffer from hypertension (control group) and patients with hypertension stage II and III (main group) was obtained. All identified differences were evaluated using the SF-36 questionnaire with the determination of a reliable difference (P) in comparison with the standards of the quality of life of practically healthy people, as well as the difference of the parameters of the quality of life of people suffering from hypertensive disease II and III stages is shown. Patients with hypertension, both among men and among women, had a decrease in the quality of life in all parameters. The most significant decrease in quality of life parameters in the main group was observed in patients of both sexes, who had a history of stage III hypertension.

If the examined patients had stage II hypertension, changes in the following indicators were recorded: pain sensations - by 56% (p<0.05), mental health - by 54% (p<0.05), role-emotional functioning - by 32% (p<0.05). At the III stage of hypertensive disease, there was a significant increase in the change of these indicators in comparison with the indicators of the control

group (pain sensations - by 72% (p<0.05), mental health - by 74% (p<0.05), role-emotional functioning - by 56% (p<0.05). As for other indicators such as: social well-being and life activity, their changes are less pronounced. In addition, after the analysis, it was found that in women, unlike men, the indicators social well-being, general health, and vitality decreased much more, especially for women with stage III hypertension (by 24.5%, 22%, and 18%, respectively, p<0.05).

30% of patients (13% of men and 17% of women) are pessimistic about the prospect of treatment, which in turn leads to anxiety and depression.

As a result of a careful study of respondents' answers to the more important questions of the questionnaire, we obtained the following: 20 respondents with II stage hypertensive disease complained of a decrease in physical and mental activity (8 men (28.5%) and 12 women (54.5%); 30 respondents (12 men (42.9%) and 14 women (63.6%) focused on rapid fatigue when performing professional and everyday activities. 60% of respondents noted various psycho-emotional disorders in themselves (15 men (53.6%) and 13 women (59%). With stage III hypertension, these indicators increase

significantly, especially pain in the form of a headache (22 men (100%) and 26 women (100%).

Conclusion.

Hypertensive disease of the II stage negatively affects the quality of life of patients, which is reflected by a decrease in pain indicators, indicators of role functioning, general state of health and indicators that characterize the psycho-emotional state of patients. With stage III hypertension, these indicators decrease much more. In addition, significant negative differences in pain indicators, role-related emotional and mental health are noted in women.

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